

Contemporary Issues and Challenges in the Indian Education System

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ABSTRACT

Education is the root of each nation. A nation won't have the capability to make due in the alert world, if its guidance framework isn't fit for contributing for its enhancement. Indian training framework is broadly criticized in multi-measurements for its inability to make required employability in its understudies as per the business prerequisites and its failure to add to comprehensive development in the country all in all. This paper deeds to feature the issues and give a few answers for purpose them.

The study utilizes optional information from different accessible sources. The analyst presumes that the issues in the present training framework that are overwhelming the development of this nation can be handled successfully if helpful and submitted moves are made by the Government to determine them.

Keywords-- Education System, Government, Issues, Quality, Solution

I. INTRODUCTION

It is for the most part publicized that India has a solid educational structure with head training. The unique measuring sticks, for example, new courses, evolving educational programs, vibrant approaches and educator preparing encourage in conveyance of value content. E-learning, understudy friendly learning, expanded appropriation of additional and co-curricular exercises, and so on in India draw in understudies from different nations, for example, China, Canada, South Africa, Germany, Canada, USA, UK and Australia. Be that as it may, in the event that one sees the employability of the yield, the status of unemployment and underemployment, the outcomes are not empowering. It is grieved that there is absence of value teaching for poor people, and just a little part of understudies, around one tenth from schools, go for higher thinks about. It is censured generally that numerous understudies consider through remembrance, and each program is arranged test situated and not learning-focused. As a result, India's teaching framework is a hindrance in accomplishing its destinations of financial improvement. This study plans to comprehend and assess the issues and difficulties in the Indian educational framework and to give arrangements.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- a) To understand the status of Indian Education System
- b) To evaluate the issues and challenges to Indian Education System

- c) To ascertain the possible solutions to resolve the issues
- d) To provide suggestions for improvement

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study yield is the result of a diagram of studies directed on the issues of Indian Education. Framework. This is fundamentally a subjective research and pursues the experiential methodology. It utilizes auxiliary information for its investigation.

IV. SCOPE OF STUDY

The examination displays the diverse structures existing in the Education Sector and their downsides. It activities to portray the issues in them and the difficulties ahead. The investigation is finished up with proposals for successful execution thinking about the vote based nature of India.

V. RESEARCH LIMITATION

Despite the fact that the examination has a striking attitude toward the issues of Indian Education System and give reasonable arrangements, they ought to be taken in to thought remembering the accompanying:

- The investigation covers a more extensive perspective of the Indian Education System. It doesn't cover the characteristic issues of each territory of India.

- The examination is done dependent on auxiliary information accessible at different sources. It needs essential information.
- The researcher has not planned to contrast Indian Education System and that of different nations.
- The arrangements are determined to a great extent dependent on the general visibility and finishes of different specialists.

VI. INDIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

India is known for its educational excellence. Indian Education has recently gained global recognition with its distinguished diversity character. Different curriculum bodies govern the school education system in India. They are:

1. The National Council of Educational Research and Training
2. The State government Boards
3. Central Board of Secondary Education
4. The Council of Indian School Certificate Examination
5. The National Institute of Open Schooling
6. Islamic Madrasah School Boards
7. Autonomous schools
8. International schools, under the International Baccalaureate, or the Cambridge There are 34 boards of secondary and senior secondary education in India (Studylib, 2017). More than 95% of the schools in India are affiliated to State Boards.

Private and Government Schools

There are schools owned by Government as well as private parties (aided and self-financed). In 2006, 19% of Indian children were privately educated. This figure jumped to 38% in 2014 (MHRD., 2016). Private schooling has been growing continuously and found desirable by the people, irrespective of their socio-economic status.

International Schools

In January 2015, the International Schools Consultancy listed India as having 410 international schools. More than 95% of the international schools offer a dual curriculum (international and a national curriculum like CBSE, ICSE or State board).

Higher Education

India has about 152 central universities, 316 state universities and 191 private universities. Other institutions include 33,623 colleges, including 1,800 exclusive women's colleges, and 12,748 institutions offering Diploma Courses (Indrail, 2015). The University Grants Commission coordinates, determines and maintains the standards of higher education at various levels. The bodies responsible for the different professional programmes are: All India Council for Technical Education, Indian Council for Agriculture Research, Distance Education Council,

National Council for Teacher Education, Bar Council of India, Medical Council of India, Indian Nursing Council, Central Council of Homeopathy, Pharmacy Council of India, Central Council of Indian Medicine and Dentist Council of India.

Open and Distance Learning

At the school level, National Institute of Open Schooling provides opportunities for continuing education to those who missed completing school education. 14 lakh students are enrolled at the secondary and higher secondary level through open and distance learning. In 2012, various state governments also introduced State Open School to provide distance education. At higher education level, Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) coordinates distance learning. It has a cumulative enrolment of 15 lakh, serviced through 53 regional centres. The Distance Education Council an authority of IGNOU is co-ordinating 13 State Open Universities and 119 institutions of correspondence courses in conventional universities.

Vocational Education

All India Council of Technical Education reported in 2013 that there were more than 4,599 vocational institutions that offer degrees, diploma and post-diploma in architecture, engineering, hotel management, infrastructure, pharmacy, technology, town services and others. Total annual intake capacity for technical diplomas and degrees exceeded 34 lakhs.

In 2016, 10 public and 10 private educational institutions were made world-class. Rs 1,000 crore budget was provided for higher education. Rs 1,700 crore was provided for 1500 multi-skill development centres. 62 new navodaya vidyalaya were created to provide quality education. A digital literacy scheme was launched for covering six crore additional rural households. The National Skill Development Mission was initiated to impart training to 76 lakh youth (India Today, 2017). Entrepreneurship training was provided across schools and colleges along with massive online courses. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan was introduced to increase focus on quality of education.

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Solution

Give more centrality to primary and secondary education - Fundamental preparing is the establishment of showing plan of a country. In case the educators at fundamental and auxiliary measurement are unskilled, not qualified and less-paid, each and every further examination will be in stake. Along these lines, more thought is required on basic guidance instead of cutting edge training. Eventually, propelled training associations battle to get quality understudies. The flimsier and less assumed schools end-up with poor understudies. This impacts ceaselessly the employability of youth, and makes a class-parcel.

Give priority to innovation in instruction -India needs to grasp PC and rapid web innovation. Our educational conveyance components should take the abundance of human cash-flow to the majority. The models of physical schools, schools and colleges should be incorporated and interlinked with ICT. The Governments ought to contribute more in innovative foundation that will facilitate the information openness.

Strengthen novelty and creativity -The framework should recompense the individuals who merits most remarkable scholastic respect. The crammers ought

not be remunerated. Our testing and stamping frameworks should be worked to perceive unique assurance, innovativeness, critical thinking also, and expansion. Positions ought to be granted in like manner.

Customize the education -Indian instruction framework is based on the presumption that if a thing is beneficial for one kid, it is useful for all. Be that as it may, one massive teaching framework can't be appropriate to all. A few people are visual students, others are sound-related students. A few children adapt quicker, some do moderate. The prospectus ought to be planned so that each student's idle capacity is distinguished and inspired. Rushed and quick learning ought to be disheartened.

Train the mentors ceaselessly -An educator is a business visionary and maker. The execution of an teacher ought not be restricted to classroom. It should be opened up for the world to see with web. There must be initiator in showing positions, not salaried individuals holding their mantle. Thus, ordinary preparing is a need.

Change the aptitude to education -Teaching occupations are generally viewed as protected, kindly compensated and hazard free employments. A large portion of the instructors don't need to change. As they wind up experienced, they get infected, and not think about the nature and need of the understudies. Understanding the present age is the need. Rules ought to be made toward this path.

Give quality education character -Teaching without character is fetus removal and will make divisions in the general public. A nation that brings down the nature of instruction and permits score rivalry in tests will rumple.

Manage dishonesty strictly -Degenerate government officials upheld by degenerate adherents and degenerate police compel are expanding. Fakes, robberies, assault and lewd behavior cases are rising. Govt enlisted bank chiefs neutralize the Govt's improvement arrangements. Printing of phony notes, presentation of plastic rice, egg, cabbage, and so forth are getting to be uncontainable. Impure is all over the place and in all things. Organic products wind up ready with synthetics. Indeed, even the little children's items are contaminated. The Govt should manage such deceitful individuals seriously.

Make education reasonable to all -On the off chance that we need to see our nation as a learning economy, we have to offer quality instruction to all and not proportioning of training. Confirmations in educational establishments ought not be on position or religion premise.

VII. CONCLUSION

Training is a country's lifeline, and it must be given more essentialness than defend in any nation. There is a basic necessity for dynamic changes in the India's guidance structure, not simply in the timetable and

technique, yet also in the temper towards the test and checks system. India can use its colossal HR advantageously if the learning structure is made fruitful. As a child is considered, it is painted with religion and position by the frightful society and is assaulted with each uneven idea and wild techniques for understanding. Every tyke has limitless potential and it should be allowed to be free from our underhanded considerations. It should be told to decrease the awkwardness. We can total a lot. However, we are not working with required genuineness. If the Govt schools are missing the mark, it is on a very basic level a consequence of non-availability or nonappearance of teachers, no executives for organization, nonattendance of exercises by educators, nonattendance of bearing to understudies, nonappearance of system, extended relationship of legislators and continuously bureaucratic control. Unconcerned gatekeepers including Govt school instructors, MPs, MLAs and priests send their wards to pvt schools. It is a shocking situation. The organization should wear down it really.

The schools Kendriya vidyalaya and Navodaya vidyalaya are vastly improved than state subsidized schools. The strategy for teaching is famous. The abilities of educators are unmatched. These schools are doing considers, giving quality guidance just as opportunity to surpass desires. No educational cost based school can organize their system; both are Govt schools with low cost. For what reason wouldn't we have the capacity to get a comparative levelheadedness in all Govt schools? Governments complete a lot in preparing, yet not bringing the results, since the undertakings are neither completely dealt with nor solid. The course of action of guidance should be understudy driven rather than check driven. Adolescents must be allowed to pick subjects according to their interests. They should be asked to ask about without any other person from library books and the Internet and offer them in the class. This will help them with creating confidence, self reliance what's more, straightforwardness to investigation. Employability is a troublesome issue today. Somehow people get degrees and end up jobless or underemployed. The idea of guidance is explicitly associated with the advantages available and it is basic for the Govt to improve resource assignment to acknowledge emotional changes in the field of instruction. Regardless of the way that the amount of understudies and activities assembles every year, India has fail to convey world class universities both in the private part or individuals by and large region. The deficiency of significant worth preparing should be avoided. The central Govt should sufficiently appropriate money to open new schools, schools and universities, update the entire system and place assets into advancement and improvement related to the guidance structure. Every youth considered in this country should have measure up to opportunity to learn, create and surpass

desires in presence with quality guidance blended with character. A dynamic nation is made by the eager youth and dynamic media. The youthful and media can make certain equitable if the officials are clear and skilled.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Indian Govt needs to put intensely in framework and instructors' training. No less than 8-10% of India's GDP must be put resources into the training part.
- Starvation influences the youngsters' capacity to learn. Neediness and sustenance lack ought to be dealt with, which is the bounden obligation of the Govt.
- Teachers ought to support originality in understudies. The last ought to be presented to monetary, natural and societal issues.
- The quality of a class ought not be more than 25 at school and 50 at advanced education. A kid can't get the required consideration of an instructor if the quality is outlandish.
- Exams ought to be tuned to survey the understudy's comprehension of the subject.
- Syllabuses learnt by understudies ought to be a similar when a similar test is to be showed up.
- Extracurricular exercises, sports movement, NSS, NCC, and so forth ought to be begun mandatorily at school level. Instruction situated trips/visits ought to be made a piece of the educational modules.
- The substance, for example, morals throughout everyday life, esteem building, comprehension of society, nationalism, enormity of pioneers and forfeits of guardians should be canvassed mandatorily in a subject in schools at each dimension.
- Teaching religions ought to be obstructed at schools.
- Quality classes, meetings and workshops ought to be sorted out to prepare the mentors to adapt up to the changing society and the changing needs of the understudies and the general public.
- Skill improvement which the Government is doing now should be fortified.
- Proper measures ought to be taken by Govt to give quality training to all at reasonable costs.
- Reservation framework and Management quantity framework be canceled. Responsibility for units by government officials and religious gatherings ought to be disheartened.

- Unwanted rivalries among instructive establishments ought to be maintained a strategic distance from.
- Media ought to wind up increasingly capable. Each news office ought to announce ordinarily no less than one occurrence on the need of value training and the change required in individuals for a sound country.
- Teaching ought to be the most generously compensated administration in the nation. Uniform pay rates ought to be paid to all educators.

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